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Assessment of the Issues of Cyber Security, Cyber Resilience and The Way Forward in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria digital technologies continue to growth and also its cyber security problems complexity has increased. Since after Covid 19 pandemic Nigeria saw a surge in cyber threats, with organization facing challenges that range from phishing attack, malware attack, ransom ware attack to insider threats. There is significant increased in cyber criminal's attack that has affect almost all sectors. twenty (20) literature were examine related to cyber security and cyber resilience were critically examine to achieved the objectives, the paper attempt to explain cyber resilience, types of cyber resilience, cyber threat that put organization at risk, it also attempt to discuss the benefits of cyber resilience. The paper recommends ways to reduce cyber security risk to organization through cyber resilience, and also suggested organization ways to improve on cyber resilience. The paper concludes that no matter how big or small an organization may be, it is not free from being under cyber attack, one of the best ways to prevent such attack is through cyber resilience.

Keywords: Assessment, Cyber Security, Cyber Resilience, Organizations.

INTRODUCTION

A Cyber threat in Nigeria has continue to evolve, businesses must take proactive measures to safeguard and protect critical assets, ensure regulatory compliance, and developed cyber resilience. Information has become a critical asset, safeguarding it has become necessary. Nigerian internet users are growing according to statista (Sasu, 2024) Nigeria had around 107 million users of internet as of February 2025, which is the highest in Africa. The figure represents 45.5% of the population having internet access. With 81% of population that access the internet are using mobile phone application to access the internet. With this figure the rate of cyber crime in Nigeria is very alarming because half of the populations have access to internet. Cyber threats can significantly pose a threat to national development by undermining national security, economic losses, reputational damage, erosion of public trust, and socio-political implication. With the dependency of the nation on technology and increase in internet usage, it is paramount for the country to develop a robust cyber security framework that can protect the entire system.

Cyber resilience refers to an organizations ability to not only withstand but also to recover from and adapt to cyber incidents, ensuring continued business operations and minimize damage. Unlike cyber security, which focuses primarily on prevention, cyber resilience acknowledges that breaches are inevitable and aims to minimize their impact.

These research paper aims to identify the critical role of cyber resilience in Nigeria and also by analyzing existing cyber security framework in an organization thereby proposing a solution. The paper also provides recommendations that would help to reduce cyber security threats.

According to Gately (2024) cyber resilience framework help organizations proactively address potential risks thereby identifying and prioritizing vulnerability and threats , this approach allow for the implementation of preventive measures to mitigate the likelihood of a successful attacks.

Types of cyber resilience

According to Synack (2025) the three types of cyber resilience are the three types of Rs (Resist, Recover, Rebuild). the three Rs is a simple framework focusing on preventing attacks , recovering from them and restoring systems afterwards.

Benefit of cyber resilience to organisations

According to Synack (2025)

1. One key advantage of cyber resilience is the ability to minimize the impact of cyber attacks. By implementing robust security measures and having effective incident response plans in place, organizations can reduce the downtime and financial losses associated with cyber incidents. This allows them to maintain business continuity and avoid reputational damage.
2. Cyber resilience enables organizations to stay ahead of the evolving threat landscape. By continuously monitoring and analyzing cyber threats, organizations can proactively identify vulnerabilities and implement necessary security measures. This proactive approach helps them to mitigate risks and prevent potential cyber attacks.

The Nigerian Government

According to a report by NCC (2025), the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), being the nation's premier communications regulatory agency under the Federal Ministry of Communications, Innovation & Digital Economy is mandated to work with all stakeholders to ensure a secure cyberspace that is safe for the operators and consumers of communications services and infrastructure in Nigeria.

In alignment with its mandate, the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) employs a multifaceted approach to address the evolving challenges of cybersecurity in Nigeria. This approach encompasses not only reactive measures, but also proactive strategies aimed at anticipating and mitigating emerging threats. By fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation, the NCC seeks to stay ahead of cyber adversaries and minimize potential disruptions to the country's communications infrastructure.

Literature Review

Cyber security within an organization involves building technological process and policies to protect systems, networks and data from cyber attracts. It's very important in safeguarding sensitive information. , maintaining continuity, also reducing financial loss. Nigeria is becoming more and more digitally connected, institutional organization find themselves at the crossroad of digital invention and the need for complete strong security framework. Studies have shown that cyber resilience is dynamic and in constant change in Nigeria system, with several attributes contributing to its compliance or non compliance. In Nigerian organizational institution cyber threat vulnerability is widely admitted and case being reported, therefore case to address these problem remain open with varying degree of success to some point.

According to Kaplan, James and Tucker (2015), the global digital economy, democracy and the public sphere now completely depend upon the stability and security of cyberspace. Encryption technologies are necessary to protect data privacy, authenticate websites and secure online transactions. Security problems such as consumer data breaches and denial-of-service attacks disrupt the digital economy and the public sphere. They also can have chilling effects on speech and online behavior.

Cyber security is one of the great human rights issues of our time. Cyber security is not only an issue for "Internet users" but for all citizens. Even someone who has never been online is directly affected when a retail company they frequent (for example, Target or Home Depot) experiences a massive consumer data breach, when their television potentially becomes a surveillance tool or when they are denied medical care because of a ransom ware attack that cryptographically locks medical records and otherwise disables

health care provider systems. All people and all societies are now directly affected by the security of digital systems (Schneier, 2016).

According to Jamie (2025) the digital age has brought significant advancements in how public sector institutions operate globally. However, with the increasing digitization of government services, the risks associated with cyber threats have become more pronounced. In Nigeria, the importance of strengthening cyber resilience in the public sector cannot be overstated. Cyber-attacks have the potential to disrupt essential services, compromise sensitive data, and even destabilize government functions.

Factor that prevent full implementation of cyber resilience in Nigeria

According to Samuel (2023) several factors affect cyber resilience in Nigeria; these include low cyber security awareness, weak infrastructures, poor network design, inadequate regulations, lack of skill cyber security professionals, rapid digitalization, and sophisticated nature of cyber attack, all these factors pose a significant challenge in achieving cyber resilience in Nigeria.

However, according to a report by Oyewole (2024) four major factors are responsible for drawback in cyber crime these include lack of promoting awareness in cyber attack, lack of strengthening cybersecurity framework, lack of legal and regulatory framework and finally capacity building.

Strategies to Strengthening Cyber Resilience in Nigeria

According to Mary Mojirade Ayantunji (2024) stated that Nigeria digital environment requires a strong and effective cyber security measures through the following:

1. Legal and regulatory framework: Nigerian government needs to create and outline defines rules and regulation of cyber crime and offences. Create a specialized cyber crime investigation division within law enforcement organization that will handle cyber crime related offences.
2. Critical infrastructure protection: by establishing and implement rules and regulations requiring strong mechanisms and frequent updates.
3. Capacity Building: by enhancing cyber security education at higher education institution by providing dedicated graduates programs that focus on cyber-security. Delivering focused training programmed for IT personals regarding evolving cyber risks, incidence response, security best practices.
4. Technical solution: by equipping the defender, such as deploying firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention system (IDS/IPS), data encryption solution to actively monitor and safeguard networks against cyber threats. Deploy vulnerability management systems to detect and rectify security vulnerability in systems and applications. By conducting thorough investigation and examination of the capabilities of technologies such as blockchain for safeguarding data storage and artificial intelligence for identifying and reducing risks.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employ in these research work involve the analysis of existing literature review. The researcher makes use of secondary sources of data to obtain information and also employed the use of qualitative interview to understand the current state of cyber resilience in Nigerian institutions and also to developed recommendations for improvement.

Interviews were conducted with key stakeholders in public and private sectors, and these include government official and in banking sectors involved in cyber security management. The aim of the interview is to get first hand information and insight into the issues affecting cyber threat and how to go about cyber resilience.

A comprehensive review of twenty (20) previous existing literatures on cyber security and cyber resilience in Nigerian institution was examine to see the strength and weakness of the institutions. These include examination of government policies, procedure and approach, and also study publications by cyber security experts. Through this analysis the researcher was able to identify some of the key challenges faced by these institutions in Nigeria and finally the researcher was able to identifies strategies that could be use to improve cyber resilience in Nigeria.

Cyber Security and Cyber Resilience in Nigeria

From the far gone discussion made no doubt cyber resilience can greatly improved cyber security institution in Nigeria:

1. Organizations in Nigeria are facing shortage of qualify cyber security professional that can handle cyber threat in case of cyber intrusion in an organization, Organization in Nigeria do not implore the use of strong data protection system and encryption measures to protect the organization from cyber threats, these finding is also in agreement with the finding of Jamie (2025) that says many government and organization in Nigeria rely on outdated IT infrastructures which is ill equipped to depend against modern cyber threats.
2. Most organization in Nigeria do not provide strategic incidence response plan to tackle incidence in case of an attack.
3. Organizations do not follow policies and procedure by conducting regular assessment test to monitor their system from vulnerability or cyber attack, this research finding is in agreement with the finding of Jamie (2025) which says that policies in Nigeria in tackling cyber threat remain inconsistence.
4. Lack of awareness on cyber attack by organization in Nigerian is also factor that prevent full implementation of cyber resilience
5. Lack of fund to combat cyber security threat in an organization in Nigeria is seriously affecting the system; this finding is also in agreement with the finding of Jamie (2025) which says that one of the primary factors that hinder organization cyber security framework is lack of adequate fund to organizations .

RECOMMENDATIONS

To facilitate and enhance cyber resilience in an organization, organization should focus mainly on the following recommendations:

1. To enhance cyber resilience in an organization in Nigeria, organization should implement strong data protection and encryption measures that include data backup, authorization, and data encryption against sensitive data to prevent unauthorized access by building strong passwords.
2. Organization in Nigeria should develop a strategic incidence response plan , these is to facilitate data recovery in case of cyber attack , the organization should design a comprehensive incidence response plan that include procedure for identifying ,controlling , and eradicate threat , as well as recover data when lost.
3. To enhance cyber resilience organization need to provide regular training of staff in recognizing and detecting suspicious activities, to limit cyber intrusion
4. Organization in Nigeria should be able to conduct regular assessments to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities.
5. To facilitate cyber resilience in Nigeria organization need to recognized cyber policies and procedure that are frequently been updated and reviewed.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result and finding of the research work , it was concluded that organization in Nigeria are facing serious challenges in dealing with cyber crime without fully implementing cyber reliance policies and procedures, most organization in Nigeria do not take preventive approach in dealing with cyber threat until after the attack, cyber resilience reorganize an organization after incidence, therefore all stake holders must come together and collaborate to facilitate cyber securities in Nigeria . Cyber resilience is a very important tool to employee in an organization to mitigate cyber threats if properly implemented.

REFERENCES

Drummond, J., Bowen, T.-J., & Hall, A.-N. (2013, 4 24). *Weebly*. Retrieved 12 04, 2022, from Weebly: <http://publicissuescomp1220uwi.weebly.com/index.html>

- Elizabeth, O. (2021). *Explainer: What You Need To Know About Bimodal Voter Accreditation System* . Lagos: Sahara Reportes Newspaper.
- Garrett, M. G. (2020). *12 cyber threat that could wreak havoc on the election*. Newyork: Wired.
- Gately, E. (2024, July 8). *TechTarget and Informa Tech's Digital Business Combine*. Retrieved December 04, 2025, from Essential Cyber Resilience Frameworks — Review & Guide: <https://www.channelfutures.com/security/what-is-a-cyber-resilience-framework>
- H., S. (2007). *Social network lunches worldwide spam Campaigns*. New York Times.
- Ibrahim, U. (2019). impact of Cybercrime on the Nigerian Economy and the Banking System. *NDIC-Quarterly* , 4.
- Inwalomhe, D. (2022). *Hackers and electronic transmission of elections result*. Lagos: Punch Newspapers.
- Jamie, I. (Feb 2025). Strengthening Cyber Resilience in Nigeria's Public. *Mengkorn-Pum* .
- Kaplan, B. J. (2015). Theory of deterrence and individual behavior. Can lawsuits control file be sharing on the Internet? *Review of Law and & Economics* 3 (3) , 693-714.
- Mary Mojirade Ayantunji, A. E. (2024). STRENGTHENING CYBERSECURITY IN NIGERIA: A HOLISTIC APPROACH. *Scientific and Practical Cyber Security Journal (SPCSJ)* 8(2): 51 – 58 ISSN 2587-4667 *Scientific* , 55.
- Meriam, I. (2022). *2023 INEC deploying technology to ensure Nigeras votes count*. Abuja: Premium Times newspaper.
- Ogala, E. (2015). *How PREMIUM TIMES survived massive cyber attacks during presidential election coverage*. Abuja: Premium Times Newspaper.
- oyewole, F. F. (2024). *Curb Cybercrime*. Washington: Forbes.
- Ron, R., Victoria, P., Richard, G., Deborah, B., & Rosalie, M. (2021, December 05). Cyber Resiliency and innovative. *Developing Cyber-Resilient Systems: A System Security Engineering Approach* , pp. NIST Special Publication 800-160, Volume 2.
- Samuel, O. (2023). *Cybersecurity Risks and Countermeasures in Nigeria*. Lagos: Vast Thinking Tech Ltd.
- Sasu, D. D. (2024). *Internet users in Nigeria 2018-2022, with forecasts up until 2027*. Germany: Statista.
- Schneier, D. &. (2016, November). *Lessons From the Dyn DDoS Attack*. Retrieved May 13, 2025, from Schneier on Security Blog.: https://www.schneier.com/blog/archives/2016/11/lessons_from_th_5.html
- Stuart, J. (2019). *Protecting Elections from cyberattack* . Washington DC: The Olive Branch.
- Ufuoma, V. (2022). *Hackers attacked our result portal during Ekiti, Osun elSection*. Ibadan: ICIR Newspaper.